

JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

ISSN: 0976-9595

Editorial Team

Editorial Board Members

Dr. Hazim Jabbar Shah Ali

Country: University of Baghdad , Abu-Ghraib , Iraq.

Specialization: Avian Physiology and Reproduction.

Dr. Khalid Nabih Zaki Rashed

Country: Dokki, Egypt.

Specialization: Pharmaceutical and Drug Industries.

Dr. Manzoor Khan Afridi

Country: Islamabad, Pakistan.

Specialization: Politics and International Relations.

Seyyed Mahdi Javazadeh

Country: Mashhad Iran.

Specialization: Agricultural Sciences.

Dr. Turapova Nargiza Ahmedovna

Country: Uzbekistan, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Specialization: Art and Humanities, Education

Dr. Muataz A. Majeed

Country: INDIA

Specialization: Atomic Physics.

Dr Zakaria Fouad Fawzy Hassan

Country: Egypt

Specialization: Agriculture and Biological

Dr. Subha Ganguly

Country: India

Specialization: Microbiology and Veterinary Sciences.

Dr. KANDURI VENKATA LAKSHMI NARASIMHACHARYULU

Country: India.

Specialization: Mathematics.

Dr. Mohammad Ebrahim

Country: Iran

Specialization: Structural Engineering

Dr. Malihe Moeini

Country: IRAN

Specialization: Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology

Dr. I. Anand shaker

Country: India.

Specialization: Clinical Biochemistry

Dr. Magdy Shayboub

Country: Taif University, Egypt

Specialization: Artificial Intelligence

Kozikhodjayev Jumakhodja Hamdamkhodjayevich

Country: Uzbekistan

Senior Lecturer, Namangan State University

Dr. Ramachandran Guruprasad

Country: National Aerospace Laboratories, Bangalore, India.

Specialization: Library and Information Science.

Dr. Alaa Kareem Niamah

Country: Iraq.

Specialization: Biotechnology and Microbiology.

Dr. Abdul Aziz

Country: Pakistan

Specialization: General Pharmacology and Applied Pharmacology.

Dr. Khalmurzaeva Nadira - Ph.D., Associate professor, Head of the Department of Japanese Philology, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Dr. Mirzakhmedova Hulkar - Ph.D., Associate professor, Head of the Department of Iranian-Afghan Philology, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies

Dr. Dilip Kumar Behara

Country: India

Specialization: Chemical Engineering, Nanotechnology, Material Science and Solar Energy.

Dr. Neda Nozari

Country: Iran

Specialization: Obesity, Gastrointestinal Diseases.

Bazarov Furkhat Odilovich

Country: Uzbekistan

Tashkent institute of finance

Shavkatjon Joraboyev Tursunqulovich

Country: Uzbekistan

Namangan State University

C/O Advanced Scientific Research,

8/21 Thamotharan Street,

Arisipalayam, Salem

THE HISTORICAL PERSONALITY OF EDIGE IN THE RESEARCH OF MEDIEVAL SCHOLARS

M.K. Maksetova

Berdakh Karakalpak State University

Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan, Republic of Uzbekistan

In the 14th–15th centuries, the Turkic-speaking tribes possessed an exceptionally rich oral folklore encompassing a wide variety of genres. Among them, folk epics occupied a special place, vividly depicting historical events of the past with features characteristic of epic poetry. In these works, the people portrayed their heroes—faithful sons—as true defenders of their homeland, ready to sacrifice their lives for their native land. The main hero of a folk epic was usually formed as an ideal embodiment of the nation’s virtues. The Turkic peoples can rightfully take pride in their world-renowned epics such as *Kitabi Dede Korkut* (The Book of My Grandfather Korkut), *Alpamys*, *Edige*, and others.

In the 15th century, the Turkic peoples who were part of the Golden Horde created the epic *Edige*. The exceptional significance of this epic, told in a vivid and colorful poetic language, lies in the fact that it serves as a living historical source about the history of the Turkic peoples during the late 14th and early 15th centuries.

The main heroes of the epic *Edige*, dedicated to the history of the Golden Horde, are Emir Timur, *Edige*, and *Tokhtamysh*.

In the Karakalpak version of the epic, *Edige*’s father is named *Baba Tukli Shashly Aziz*, who leads an ascetic life near a cemetery. One day, he hides the clothing of a *peri* (a fairy) who flew down in the form of a dove and marries her. However, due to his failure to fulfill a condition set by the *peri*, *Baba Tukli Aziz* loses his wife. As the pregnant *peri* departs, she says: “I am already with child; you will find our baby at such-and-such a time, in such-and-such a place.” According to the Karakalpak version, this child—born of the *peri* and abandoned by her—is discovered by a maidservant belonging to a man named *Toman Khoja*.

The foundling is brought to the khan to be given a name. The khan is astonished at the garments the child is wrapped in. Gazing into the boy's face, Tokhtamysh takes the child, declaring, "The foundling belongs to the khan." Tokhtamysh's wife, Karashash, nurses and raises him, feeding him mare's milk. The boy is named Edige.

As he grows up, Edige studies at school. When he reaches the age of eighteen, he is married to a girl from the lineage of khojas named Karakas. The khan entrusts Edige with herding a thousand horses in a place called Karakol. Thus begins Edige's independent path as a hardworking man.

As for the miraculous birth of Edige in the epic, it reflects the use of supernatural motifs typical of folk epics. Folk imagination and real-life motifs are remarkably interwoven and harmonious. The realistic elements blend with the fantastic, while the events are depicted as truly having occurred. The narration is so subtle and convincing that the audience never doubts the authenticity of the story.

Indeed, the historical Edige appeared on the political stage alongside Tokhtamysh. He was a descendant of the Mangit clan, one of the most influential emirs and aristocrats of the Golden Horde. His lineage was not connected with the descendants of Genghis Khan.

Abulgazi Bahadur Khan, in his famous book *Shajara-i Turk* (The Genealogy of the Turks), provides the following information about Edige's early life:

"There was a man named Kutlukiya from the Mangit tribe. He had a son and a daughter. His daughter married Timurbek Ogland, and their son was Timur Kutlug Khan. Kutlukiya's son was named Edige. He became a warrior (nuker) of Tokhtamysh Khan. At that time, Tokhtamysh fled from Urus Khan and came to Timur Beg in Samarkand. Edige, from the Mangit tribe, arrived soon after and reported that Urus Khan had gathered his army for a campaign. With the help of Timur Beg, Tokhtamysh defeated Urus Khan, subjugated the Jochid population, and ascended the throne in Sarai. Later, when Timur Kutlug moved to Tamiz, Edige left Tokhtamysh and joined Timur Kutlug, who was related to him by blood. Timur Kutlug secretly aspired to kingship, which led to conflict with Tokhtamysh Khan.

Tokhtamysh planned to capture and kill him, but Timur Kutlug escaped and fled to Timur Beg. Edige, having separated from Timur Kutlug, rejoined him after six months.” [2, p. 99]

These words of Abulgazi Bahadur Khan indeed clarify the biography of Edige. Moreover, his account coincides with almost all other historical sources from that period.

It should be noted that in many of these sources, Edige’s clan is identified as Mangit—exactly as it is in the epic. However, Ibn Arabshah, in his aforementioned work, expresses a slightly different view:

“Emir Idiku, one of the leaders of the left wing emirs and the courtiers who were wise and prudent men, resided at Tokhtamysh’s court. His tribe was called Kungirat, which included various sub-tribes and dialects similar to those of the Turks and Arabs.” [5, p. 49]

In some other sources, Edige is also referred to as an “Uzbek.”

According to Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, who relied on ancient Iranian sources, the father of Edige was Baltichak (Balynzhak), the chief emir of Timur Malik.

One of the well-known researchers of the epic Edige, V.M. Zhirmunsky, writes about this in his book dedicated to the epics of the Turkic peoples:

“When Timur Malik was defeated and killed by Tokhtamysh, the anonymous chronicler of Iskender narrates that Baltichak, having been captured and put in chains, was brought to the court of Tokhtamysh. Since his loyalty and honesty were well known, Tokhtamysh said to him: ‘If you recognize me as your sovereign, I will not deviate by even a hair’s breadth from showing you respect and honor. I will entrust to your care the reins of governance over the kingdom and its wealth.’ Baltichak trembled and replied: ‘If my hands were not bound, I would answer you differently. May the eye that can see you in the place of my sovereign be blinded! If power is truly in your hands, then order that I be executed, so that the head of the sovereign may rest upon my head and his body upon my body — for if I have not died before

him, then at least let me be delivered to dust before him.’ Tokhtamysh granted his request.” [4, p. 364]

The constant quarrels and conflicts between Edige and Tokhtamysh, as well as the active support Edige provided to Timur Kutlug, the son of Timur Malik, can evidently be explained by the fact that Edige inherited his father’s feelings of loyalty and hostility toward the aforementioned khans. Naturally, after Tokhtamysh killed Edige’s father, both men began to treat each other with growing distrust. Abulgazi Bahadur Khan also notes how close Timur Kutlug and Edige were, and how inseparable their friendship became.

The circumstances that led to Edige’s departure for the land of Satemir are described quite differently in the epic. Tokhtamysh’s wife fears that Edige, once grown, might seize her husband’s throne. She drives a wedge between them, spreading rumors and constantly warning Tokhtamysh that Edige, powerful and ambitious, might one day usurp the throne and even marry his daughters. Conspiring with her husband, the khan’s wife plots to kill Edige by poisoning his wine. This treacherous scheme fails.

After consulting with his beys, the khan decides to hold a grand feast, get Edige drunk, and murder him — but this truly devilish plan also fails. Unable to endure the constant tension and danger of the khan’s repeated attempts on his life, Edige decides to leave for the land of Satemir. His loyal friends, Angysin and Tyngysin, help him escape the trap laid by the khan.

Although Edige leaves his native Nogai land, he feels deep sorrow at parting with it. He still hopes that Tokhtamysh might send a messenger to recall him. Edige reasons that if the khan sends a nobleman, it would be a sign of goodwill and reconciliation, and he could safely return; but if the khan sends a slave, it would mean ill intentions and he must never return. When the khan sends his vizier Kenzhembai, a man of servile origin, Edige realizes the danger and departs from the Nogai steppe to the land of Satemir.

As noted above, there is a specific creative pattern in the formation of an epic. Even in the structure and sequence of events, the intentions, reflections, and imagination of the epic's creators are evident. The episode of Edige's departure from the Nogai land is rendered with remarkable artistic power, which lends it great authenticity and emotional depth. The scene is portrayed so vividly and concisely that nothing could be added or removed without diminishing its impact.

Nevertheless, even within the artistic framework of the epic, essential elements of historical reality can still be discerned. The fact that the authors do not merely enumerate historical events but instead vividly depict Tokhtamysh's fear and suspicion toward Edige convincingly demonstrates how skillfully and realistically the Edige epic was composed. Thus, we again witness the remarkable comprehensiveness and depth of the creators' vision.

In the epic, Edige appears as a courageous and valiant hero, equally skilled in archery and swordsmanship. He is portrayed as eloquent, wise, and unmatched in resolving complex disputes and judgments — and also as a man of striking appearance.

The Arab historian Ibn Arabshah, who wrote a book about Timur and visited his court, saw Edige with his own eyes. He describes Edige as follows:

“Idiku was a swarthy man of medium height, with a stout body. He was brave and possessed the power to influence those around him. He was a great man, distinguished by generosity, and his smile was warm. Idiku stood out for the reliability of his words and judgments. He showed kindness to scholars, welcomed intelligent and learned men, and jested with them gracefully, using the most charming turns of speech and delicate gestures.” [5, p. 163]

Describing Edige and dwelling on his remarkable qualities, Ibn Arabshah writes:

“There are extraordinary stories and unique, astonishing accounts about Edige. The deadly arrows he shot struck his enemies with precision; his cunning military tactics consisted of setting traps and ambushes. There exist his valuable reflections on

the methods of logically sound politics, the discussion of which lies beyond the scope of our narrative” [5, p.163].

According to Arabshah, with Timur’s full support, Edigey himself appointed the commanders and leaders of the left wing of the army under his control, thereby attaining such a powerful position that even the proclamation of any new khan did not take place without his will. He gained great authority and influence both among his compatriots and in the eyes of Timur.

The epic does not mention Edigey’s campaigns against Khorezm, Moscow, or Lithuania. According to Abdurazzak Samarkandi, Edigey managed to completely conquer Khorezm between December 22, 1405, and January 21, 1406. Leaving Amir Anko as the ruler of Khorezm, Edigey himself returned to Deshti Kipchak. Anko’s rule in Khorezm lasted until 1408–1409, until the death of Shadikhan (Shadybek) and the accession of Polatkhan to the khan’s throne. During Polatkhan’s reign, Edigey recalled Anko and appointed Bagalka as the new ruler of Khorezm.

In 1411, after Polatkhan’s death, the throne was taken by Timur Khan, son of Timur Kutlug, who began a fierce enmity with Edigey. Having suffered defeat from Timur Khan, Edigey fled to Khorezm. There he gathered troops and then set out toward the ulus, that is, the Golden Horde. In a place called Sam, located ten days’ journey from Khorezm, he encountered the troops of Azhak Bahadur and Gazan, sent by Timur Khan against him, and engaged in battle. During this battle, Bagalja, the ruler of Khorezm, was killed, and Edigey himself was wounded and returned to Khorezm. This occurred in April–May 1411. Dakana and Gazan, pursuing Edigey as far as Khorezm, laid siege to the capital of this state for six months.

At that time, news arrived that Sultan Jalal ad-Din, son of Tokhtamysh Khan, had attacked Timur Khan, destroyed his capital, and that Timur Khan was on his way to Khorezm. Meanwhile, a messenger from Sultan Jalal ad-Din arrived and immediately conveyed the following order from his ruler:

“Until now, Timur Khan was khan, and you fought with the sword for him. From now on, I am khan—fight with all your might for me and capture our enemy Edigey.”

Sultan Jalal ad-Din also sent another messenger with the following message:

“If Edigey releases his son Sultan Mahmud and my younger sister, who is married to his son, and orders coins to be minted and the Friday prayer (khutbah) to be proclaimed in my name, do not fight him—return at once.”

Gazan, who was married to Sultan Jalal ad-Din’s younger sister, was ready to conclude a peace agreement. But Dakana, who was married to Timur Khan’s younger sister, pretended not to know about this order. At that time, the ill-fated Timur Khan was already approaching Khorezm. Gazan, leaving Dakana to indulge in drinking, sent his retainer Zhankhodzha, who killed the unfortunate Timur Khan.

Hearing of this, Sultan Jalal ad-Din, filled with gratitude toward Gazan, sent a letter which read:

“Gazan is our khan; obey his orders as if they were my own.”

Among the emirs besieging the capital of Khorezm, the most noble by lineage and status was Khizir Oglan, followed by Dakana, and lastly Gazan. However, Gazan, having killed Timur Khan, now rose above them all and occupied an exceptionally privileged position.

Emir Edigey made an agreement with them, after which they left the city walls and held a feast in honor of each other. The emirs lifted the siege and set out to meet Sultan Jalal ad-Din.

Kazhulay the hero caught up with them in a place called Balukiya and reproached them, saying:

“Why are you returning without capturing Khorezm?”

The emirs replied:

“Although we besieged Khorezm with an army of ten thousand for seven months, we could not take it. And you have no more than three to four thousand men.

It is better to turn back—besides, we have made an agreement. Edigey will send his son to the khan.”

But Kazhulay boasted arrogantly:

“It will take just one breath from me—and Edigey will be gone!” With these words, he headed toward Khorezm.

Knowing this, Emir Edigey set out against him. Since his army was relatively small, he resorted to a cunning stratagem: he moved at night and hid in secret places during the day. When the two armies approached each other, Emir Edigey divided his soldiers into two groups. He instructed one group that, upon encountering the enemy, they should not engage in a real battle but pretend to flee in disorder. Edigey ordered them strictly to scatter horse gear—saddles, blankets, bags, and other items—as if they were abandoning rich spoils in haste.

As soon as Emir Kazhulay arrived, Edigey’s men, barely beginning the fight, pretended to flee. Kazhulay’s troops, believing them to be the main enemy force, rushed in pursuit to seize the supposed spoils. At that very moment, Emir Edigey suddenly appeared with his own troops, brandishing gleaming spears. The soldiers of Kazhulay, who had been chasing the fleeing men, were forced to halt their horses and engage in combat with Edigey’s warriors, who struck from ambush. No matter how desperately Kazhulay fought, in the end he was killed. Emir Edigey cut off his head and sent it to Khorezm, ordering that Kazhulay’s banner be raised again and his trumpeters play their horns loudly. The group of Kazhulay’s warriors who had ridden far ahead in pursuit of the “spoils,” seeing their banner, began to return in small groups. About a thousand of them, arriving separately, were captured. Thus Edigey’s troops returned to Khorezm with rich spoils.

After securely locking up all the captured enemy soldiers, Edigey gave his guards a strict order:

“If any of them escapes, the guard responsible will be executed, and his house will be completely destroyed.”

Continuing his account, Abdurazzak Samarkandi reports the following. In that same year, 1413, Shahrukh, the son of Timur and ruler of Khorasan, prepared an army to march on Khorezm. The Khorasani emirs Aliko and Ilyaskhoja, with a large and select army, set out toward Khorezm. The emir Musaka also departed from Maverannahr with five thousand horsemen. The two armies joined near Khorezm. At that time, the ruler of Khorezm was Mubarakshah, son of Edigey, while Bekizhek held the positions of chief of the palace chancery and qadi (judge).

Realizing that enemy forces were approaching, they began to deliberate on what to do. Some advised concluding a peace agreement, others suggested leaving the city, and still others proposed fighting the enemy. Emir Aliko sent an envoy to the approaching forces, managing to calm them somewhat and, as it seemed, win their favor. Gifts were prepared by those who supported peace negotiations. At that moment, the troops of Emir Said Ali and Emir Ilyaskhoja approached those bringing gifts, capturing some and killing others. Thus, the Khorezmians found themselves in a critical situation, and battle began.

However, hearing the word “agreement,” some of the Khorezmian troops had already scattered in confusion. Even so, that day the Khorezmians fought from morning until evening against the forces sent by Shahrukh. By evening, news spread: “Emir Edigey and Chingiz Oglan have arrived,” and joyful music began to play. The emirs, who had experienced the exceptional bravery of the Khorezmians during the day and then heard of Edigey’s arrival in the evening, turned their horses back that same night, while the Khorezmians, pursuing them closely, captured their baggage as spoils [1, 179–182].

Upon hearing this, Shahrukh immediately sent an army led by Said Ali Tarkhan and Shahmalik, joining to them the troops from Maverannahr, and dispatched them to seize Khorezm. Unable to withstand such a great force, Mubarakshah, ruler of Khorezm and son of Edigey, fled to his father [1, 182].

Thus, Edigey’s rule over Khorezm lasted until 1413. Edigey, one of the most powerful emirs of the Golden Horde, ruled Khorezm beginning in 1405.

As Abdurazzak Samarkandi notes, Shahrukh Mirza preferred to maintain friendly relations with the khans of the Golden Horde. In his palace, he received the envoys of Polatkhan, Edigey, and Ibsay with great honor. The envoys presented Shahrukh Mirza with gifts—falcons, other hunting birds, and various offerings. Shahrukh Mirza, in turn, showed them respect and presented them with gold-embroidered belts. He also prepared special gifts for Polatkhan, Edigey, and Ibsay, and then decided to send one of his close associates, Emir Hasanku, to Polatkhan. At that time, Shahrukh Mirza intended to marry his son, Prince Muhammad Juchi Bahadur, to Edigey's daughter [1, 139].

In his efforts to strengthen the Golden Horde, Edigey waged fierce struggles against its enemies. This was particularly evident in his campaigns against the Lithuanian prince Vytautas. In the Karakalpak version of the epic “Edigey,” however, there is no mention of Edigey's campaigns against Lithuania or Moscow. It is remarkable that, although these events truly occurred in history, they somehow escaped the attention of the epic's creators—perhaps for specific reasons.

The sayings of Edigey, filled with worldly wisdom and moral instruction, became widespread among the people and were firmly woven into the artistic fabric of the epic. Edigey is that legendary great hero of the Turkic peoples who, at the end of the 14th and beginning of the 15th century, ruled the Golden Horde for a quarter of a century—an exceptionally wise, brave, and courageous man who devoted all his strength and intellect to consolidating his state. His deeds, his justice, and his skill in resolving disputes won the admiration of the people. That is why the people loved him and created an epic about him. This alone shows how deeply Edigey is rooted in the hearts of the Turkic peoples.

References

1. Абдуразак Самарканди. Матлаи саъдайн ва мажмаи бахрайн. Ташкент.: 1969. – 575 с
2. Абулгозий Баходирхон. Шажарайи турк. -Ташкент: «Чулпон», 1990. – 192 с
3. Едиге. Нөкис.: 1990. 400 с.
4. Жирмунский В.М. Тюркский героический эпос. Ленинград.: «Наука», 1974. – 728 с

5.Ибн Арабшах. Амир Темур тарихи. Тошкент.: «Меҳнат», 1992. –192 с